

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2006–2007

DIRECTORS, JULY 1, 2006–JUNE 30, 2007

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, had advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2006–2007

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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JESSICA WADE
Administrative Associate

LETTER FROM THE CHAIRPERSON

Paula Kaufman
Chairman of the Board

Exciting things are happening at CLIR. Since my election as chairperson of the Board last November, much has changed for our organization. It has been a year of exceptional growth and rewards. In November, the Board appointed Charles Henry as CLIR's new president. We recognized that Chuck, trained in the humanities, and with experience in library leadership, computational sciences, and publishing, has the unique skills and background needed to lead us in new directions.

Chuck set forth his vision for the organization in a major funding proposal submitted to The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation in late 2006. The Foundation's decision to fund the proposal, CLIR's most significant award in several years, marked the start of a new, three-year agenda that focuses on evolving scholarship and the infrastructure needed to support it.

Also in the past year, two important appointments have added significant depth to our staff. The arrival of Amy Friedlander as program director in April and the appointment of Michael Keller as presidential fellow in July will enable us to more fully explore a range of topics central to our new agenda.

Amid these developments, we have continued to strengthen our established programs and activities, such as the Frye Leadership Institute and the Postdoctoral Fellowships in Scholarly Information Resources.

Under new leadership and with new staff members, we are well positioned to advance the pivotal issues affecting academic libraries and the scholarly community at large. In so doing, we are working from a long tradition of catalyzing change and of leading responses to emerging challenges in the profession.

I look to the year ahead with great confidence.

Paula Kaufman
September 2007

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

THIS FORUM FOR CHANGE

What are the strongest contributions CLIR has made to its constituency over the years? What new directions can build upon and be sustained by these traditional strengths? Those were the two questions I asked myself some nine months ago when preparing to become president of this organization.

My answer to the first question—or at least one answer, since CLIR’s contributions are numerous—was the rigor and breadth of our research program. CLIR has traditionally asked difficult questions, convened the best minds to address and help structure a response to these questions, and contracted with leading researchers to explore the nature and implications of the challenges that confront us. These elements—the penetrating questions and the vigorous response—will remain essential to our mission.

As I pondered the second question—new directions for CLIR—I recognized that our traditional areas of focus, such as preservation, access, scholarly communication, leadership, and the evolution of the digital library, were as timely as ever and that they required further study. At the same time, new areas of research, including cyberinfrastructure, emerging scholarly methodologies, and the potential for new organizational models in higher education, also seemed appropriate. They offer additional opportunities for exploring areas of consequence and interest to our constituencies.

Another distinguishing feature of CLIR’s new research and program agenda has also been appropriated from past practice: a thorough integration of these lines of inquiry. CLIR’s new agenda rests on the interrelationship of its areas of programmatic focus, just as has CLIR’s strategic direction over the past decade. But while this approach brings continuity to CLIR’s mission, the environment in which we are working is different from that of the past. We are wrestling with systemic transformation and need to develop solutions on an astonishing scale in order to facilitate research and teaching and to foster intellectual productivity. While CLIR has traditionally contributed foundational aspects of research in its publications, forums, and proceedings, the implications for changes in the academy are profoundly encompassing. We find ourselves today in a new environment that requires a new architecture. It is an environment whose volumes, functional clarity, and programs are virtual. It is a digital world

that will complement, and perhaps largely replace, the analog spaces we have comfortably inhabited for millennia.

CLIR's agenda continues to be a weave of interrelated themes and subjects, which positions our organization well to look at issues in terms of their connections. To respond effectively to the challenges that we now face, however, the communities participating in the new research agenda must be broadened. This will require deliberate effort, for a new scholarly environment does not simply appear. It must be built—by librarians, scholars, engineers, legislators, and administrators. An unprecedented pooling of talent and perspectives will be required. The chief goal of such a collaborative effort, which CLIR is well suited to help organize, structure, and sustain, is the instantiation of a digital environment in which we can ask new, exciting questions, conduct new research, make new discoveries, and, if we do this well, gain a more nuanced understanding of the human condition: within the ghostlier demarcations of a digital world, a keener appreciation of what we are becoming.

Charles Henry
September 2007

THE PROGRAMS

In March 2007, CLIR announced a new three-year agenda, supported by a significant grant from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The agenda, influenced by a series of meetings and discussions throughout 2006, deepens CLIR's traditional work in scholarly communications, preservation, leadership, and the emerging library, while also strengthening their interconnections. At the same time, the new agenda integrates CLIR's work more tightly with efforts to develop a cyberinfrastructure that will promote, sustain, and advance research and teaching in the humanities and social sciences.

Since March, the CLIR staff has been laying the foundation for new partnerships with foundations and other organizations that will play key roles in cyberinfrastructure development. For example, CLIR anticipates new collaboration with the National Endowment for the Humanities, which recently launched a formal initiative in the digital humanities. CLIR is also serving on the executive team of the National Science Foundation Blue Ribbon Task Force on Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access. Meanwhile, CLIR is exploring new venues for generating discussions of cyberinfrastructure. For example, CLIR Director of Programs Amy Friedlander was invited to guest-edit a forthcoming issue of *Journal of Electronic Publishing* that will focus on communication and cyberinfrastructure.

The following pages provide an overview of activity between July 1, 2006, and June 30, 2007.

Survey of Digital Humanities Centers in the United States

In May, CLIR commissioned information management consultant Diane Zorich to survey selected digital humanities centers. The survey will investigate the scope of these centers and their financing, organizational structure, products, services, and sustainability.

The survey will be conducted in a phased, iterative fashion. An initial exploratory phase will identify the organizations to be surveyed, the topics to be covered, the survey methodology, and the survey instrument. The second phase will consist of data collection and analysis and preparation of a final report.

Study findings will be used to inform the 2008 Scholarly Communications Institute. The Institute, to be held at the University of Virginia, will be devoted to assessing the needs, priorities, and challenges of national digital humanities centers. The report will also inform the national debate over the structure and function of these centers, as called for in *Our Cultural Commonwealth*, a report issued in 2007 by the American Council of Learned Societies.

National Digital Information Infrastructure Preservation Program/Library of Congress

In 2006–2007, CLIR continued to work in partnership with the Library of Congress's National Digital Information Infrastructure Preservation Program.

As part of this collaborative effort, CLIR provided editorial support for the final report of the working group on revisions to Section 108 of the Copyright Act. The CLIR staff also provided support to the Motion Picture, Broadcast, and Recorded Sound Division, commissioning Columbia University legal scholar June Besek to write a report on copyright issues relating to the preservation of and access to pre-1972 unpublished audio recordings.

National Science Foundation/Blue Ribbon Task Force on Sustainable Digital Preservation

In June, CLIR was invited to become a contributing partner in a National Science Foundation (NSF) Blue Ribbon Task Force on Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access, which will undertake a two-year study on the economics of sustainable digital preservation. The task force is charged with developing recommendations for promoting the economic sustainability of digital information for the academic, public, and private sectors. The task force also plans to produce a series of articles about the challenges and opportunities of digital information preservation for both the scholarly community and the public. CLIR Director of Programs Amy Friedlander, a member of the task force's executive team, will write the first-year report, anticipated for release by early 2009.

In addition to the NSF, sponsors of the task force include The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the Joint Information Systems Committee, and the Library of Congress.

Faculty Research Behavior Workshops

In 2007, CLIR offered, for the first time, workshops on ethnographic techniques for gathering information about the faculty research process. Two such workshops were held. Led by University of Rochester anthropologist Nancy Foster, workshop participants learned skills for observing faculty

Frye Institute Participants Class of 2007

Debra Allison, Miami University
 James Beattie, University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
 Tracy Chapman, Creighton University
 Sarah Cheverton, James Madison University
 Richard Darga, Chicago State University
 Alison Davis-Tariq, Norfolk State University
 Kathy Fernandes, California State University, Chico
 Megan Fitch, Kenyon College
 Alan Foley, University of Wisconsin
 Patterson Graham, University of Georgia
 Norma Grijalva, New Mexico State University
 Roberta Gwilt, Syracuse University Library
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 Kitty McNeill, Emory University
 Daniel Noonan, The Ohio State University
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 Michael Spalti, Willamette University
 Thomas Steffes, Earlham College
 Lisa Trubitt, University at Albany-State University of
 New York
 Deon van der Merwe, University of South Africa
 Brenda van Gelder, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and
 State University
 Xuemao Wang, Johns Hopkins University
 Dave Wedaman, Brandeis University
 Eric Williams-Bergen, St. Lawrence University
 Michael Winkler, University of Pennsylvania
 Melissa Woo, University of Illinois at Urbana-
 Champaign
 Sherri Yerk-Zwickl, Lehigh University
 James Young, Harrisburg University of Science and
 Technology
 Lily Zhang, Randolph-Macon College

behavior, interviewed faculty members, and analyzed the results of those interviews. At the end of the workshop, they planned how they would apply their new skills at their home institutions.

Liberal arts colleges with merged library instruction and information technology (IT) units were invited to send a staff member to one of the workshops. The first workshop was held at Wesleyan University in February; the second was held at Kenyon College in April. CLIR will continue to offer the two-day workshops at academic institutions across the country.

Frye Leadership Institute

The Frye Leadership Institute is designed to develop leaders who can guide and transform academic information services for higher education. The institute, which CLIR sponsors with EDUCAUSE and Emory University, is now in its eighth year. It has trained more than 350 librarians, faculty members, and IT experts.

The 2007 institute was held June 3–14 at the Emory Conference Center in Atlanta, Georgia. The 46 participants came from research universities, master's degree institutions, liberal arts colleges, and community colleges. Five participants came from universities abroad. Susan Perry, former CLIR interim president, and EDUCAUSE President Brian Hawkins served as deans.

The Frye Institute is supported with funds from the Robert W. Woodruff Foundation.

Chief Information Officers

CLIR facilitates a semiannual forum that enables chief information officers (CIOs) of merged library and computing units in liberal arts colleges to discuss issues affecting teaching and learning on their campuses. The 35 members use their meetings and a listserv to share information on such topics as recent changes in merged organizations, college Web sites and their policies governing content and archiving practices, handling of copyright infringement notices, and job descriptions.

In 2005, the group developed a Web-based survey designed to measure how students, faculty, and staff use and evaluate the services and resources of merged library and computing units. Members can use the survey instrument to gauge their effectiveness. They continue to analyze the results and to share their findings with the community at large.

This year the CIOs started the Work Exchange Database, a resource for IT and library managers that provides midlevel career-development opportunities for staff. The database enables institutions to offer and seek expertise and exchange staff.

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

The Academic Librarians Advisory Committee was formed to advise CLIR on issues of relevance to libraries at colleges and small and midsize universities. Members, who represent both public and private institutions, met twice this year to discuss professional development for library directors, how to work with consultants on library space planning, off-site storage, and information-literacy assessments, such as the National Survey of Student Engagement, and what the results of such assessments mean for libraries. Connie Vinita Dowell, dean of libraries and information access at San Diego State University, chairs the group.

AWARDS

Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources

The Mellon Dissertation Fellowship program supports original-source doctoral research in libraries and archives, without regard to the location or format of those sources. Established in 2001 and administered by CLIR, the program awards 10 to 15 annual fellowships of up to \$20,000 each. In 2007, 13 fellows were selected from more than 360 candidates. As in years past, the fellows proposed work in a wide range of repositories; their topics of study were similarly broad in scope. In May, the fellows convened at the Library of Congress for a one-day workshop on research in archives and special collections.

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Scholarly Information Resources

In May, five individuals were awarded Postdoctoral Fellowships in Scholarly Information Resources for 2007–08. The fellows, each of whom recently received a Ph.D. degree in the humanities, will spend the year at an academic research library, where they will gain hands-on experience relating to the issues facing scholars at research libraries. Six fellows from 2006–07 will continue in the program for a second year, bringing the total number of CLIR fellows to 11 for 2007–08.

CLIR created this program in response to changes in scholarly communication and a growing need to develop linkages between disciplinary scholarship, libraries, archives, and evolving digital tools. Fellows reside at their host institutions and undertake such projects as the development of writing and research guides for students, the design and implementation of metadata standards for faculty using digital visual resources, improving library sites and portals to reflect undergraduate-user patterns, and advising on and contributing to inventories of digital projects in area collections.

Bryn Mawr's Library Director and Chief Information Officer Elliott Shore is dean of the fellowship program. In summer 2006, he led an orientation

2007 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Jeffrey Ahlman, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, History
Daniel Amsterdam, University of Pennsylvania, History
Peter Broadwell, University of California, Los Angeles, Musicology
Daniel Domingues de Silva, Emory University, History
David Hunter, University of Maryland, College Park, History
Rebecca Johnson, Yale University, Comparative Literature
Ryan Kashaipour, University of Arizona, History
Fabiola Lopez-Duran, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Art and Architecture
Vanessa Mongey, University of Pennsylvania, History
Catherine Styer, University of Pennsylvania, History
Nu-Anh Tran, University of California, Berkeley, History
Uranchimeg Tsultem, University of California, Berkeley, History
Mari Webel, Columbia University, History

2007–2008 Fellows in Scholarly Information Resources

<i>Fellow</i>	<i>Fellowship Host Institution</i>
Lauren Coats	Lehigh University
Danielle Culpepper	Johns Hopkins University
Erica Doerehoff	Pepperdine University
Caroline E. Kelley	UCLA
Cecily Marcus	University of Minnesota
Lori Miller	Appalachian College Association
Wesley Raabe	University of Nebraska- Lincoln
Timothy Stinson	Johns Hopkins University
Elizabeth Waraksa	UCLA
Susan L. Wiesner	University of Virginia
Tracie Wilson	Bryn Mawr College

seminar that all fellows attended before starting their assignments. He advised the fellows throughout the year on work in progress and organized virtual seminars with leading figures in librarianship, the humanities, and other related areas.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Lorraine Alison Dong, a master's degree candidate in the School of Information at the University of Texas at Austin, was selected for the Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship, which enabled her to attend the 2007 World Library and Information Congress in South Africa. She is studying preservation administration while working toward a graduate portfolio in nonprofit studies at the LBJ School of Public Affairs' RGK Center for Philanthropy and Community Service. Ms. Dong has a M.Phil. degree in Renaissance literature from the University of Cambridge in England and a B.A. in English literature with a minor in education from the University of California at Berkeley.

Mathilde and Howard Rovelstad provide funding for this scholarship.

A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management

Alvin K. Cheung, a doctoral student in computer science at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, was named the recipient of the 2007 A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management. Mr. Cheung's research focuses on the collection and processing of contextual information called ContextDB. He holds bachelor's degrees in electrical engineering and music and a master's degree in electrical engineering from Stanford University.

Named in honor of A. R. Zipf, a pioneer in information management systems, the fellowship is awarded annually to a student who is enrolled in graduate school, is in the early stages of study, and shows exceptional promise for leadership and technical achievement in information management.

PUBLICATIONS

Preservation in the Age of Large-Scale Digitization

The digitization of millions of books under programs such as Google Book Search and Microsoft Live Search Books is dramatically expanding our ability to search and find information. For scholars, it is the unparalleled scale of these undertakings that holds such promise. That very scale, however, has given rise to concerns about the quality and long-term accessibility of digitized material.

In May, CLIR commissioned Oya Rieger, interim assistant university librarian for digital library and information technologies at Cornell Univer-

sity Library, to examine large-scale digital initiatives and to identify issues that will influence the availability and usability, over time, of the digital books that these projects create. The report was circulated for comment and will be published early in 2008.

The Whole Digital Library Handbook

In February 2007, American Library Association Publishing released *The Whole Digital Library Handbook*, edited by Diane Kresh under commission from CLIR. The handbook is a comprehensive guide for anyone who manages, works in, or uses digital collections. It contains facts, tips, and miscellanea on the current state of digital collections and on where the field is headed.

Census of Institutional Repositories

Published in February, *Census of Institutional Repositories in the United States* is the product of an extensive survey conducted in 2006 by Karen Markey, Soo Young Rieh, Beth St. Jean, Jihyun Kim, and Elizabeth Yakel at the University of Michigan. The authors investigated the development of institutional repositories in colleges and universities with the aim of identifying models and best practices in the administration, technical infrastructure, and access policies of repository collections.

The census was a first step in the larger MIRACLE (Making Institutional Repositories in A Collaborative Learning Environment) project, whose aim is to identify specific factors contributing to the success of institutional repositories and effective ways of accessing and using repositories. The report is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub140abst.html>.

Library Workflow Redesign: Six Case Studies

The proliferation of electronic information and tools has changed the way in which readers and researchers do their work. It has also changed the way in which library staff members provide materials and services. While technology now makes it possible to deliver more content and services, libraries are often expected to do so with little or no increase in funding, or even with reduced budgets.

Beginning in 2002, with support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR offered workflow redesign support to teams from six liberal arts colleges that are part of consortia. One outcome of that work was a publication called *Library Workflow Redesign: Six Case Studies*. Edited by Marilyn Mitchell and published in January 2007, the report describes in detail the workflow redesign projects undertaken by the six libraries and includes a series of recommendations based on lessons learned. The report is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub139abst.html>.

E-Journal Archiving Metes and Bounds: A Survey of the Landscape

The growth of e-journal publication and users' increasing dependence on electronic resources poses an urgent question to institutions of higher education: how can we ensure the long-term availability of e-journal content? To develop a response to this question, CLIR commissioned Anne R. Kenney, Richard Entlich, Peter B. Hirtle, Nancy Y. McGovern, and Ellie L. Buckley to undertake a survey of 12 e-journal archiving initiatives. The report, *E-Journal Archiving Metes and Bounds: A Survey of the Landscape*, is intended to help libraries better understand the emerging strategies and options for ensuring long-term access to born-digital scholarly literature and to help them determine the most appropriate course of action for their individual circumstances. The report is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub138abst.html>.

Art History and Its Publications in the Electronic Age

This report, copublished in September with Rice University Press, examines how changes in scholarly publishing are affecting the field of art history. The report's authors, Hilary Ballon and Mariët Westermann, found that while monograph publishing is in retrenchment, new publication opportunities are emerging, thanks to the improved quality of digital images and new modes of electronic publication. The authors conclude that these opportunities may offer economic benefits to academic publishers in both print and electronic media. The report is available at <http://cnx.org/content/m13916/latest/>.

ADVISORY GROUPS

AS OF JUNE 30, 2007

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Diane Parr Walker
University of Virginia

Eugene Wiemers
Bates College

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN FY 2007

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Brooks, Connie San Marcos, TX	To serve as expert consultant to advise on the development of CLIR's preservation agenda	8/1/2006	\$24,700
Columbia University New York, NY	To write an analysis of copyright with respect to pre-1972 unpublished recorded sound	4/2/2007	\$4,500
Cornell University Library Ithaca, NY	To prepare a report on third-party repositories for electronic serials	2/17/2006	\$33,300
Crandall, Mike Seattle, WA	To give technical advice and assistance to Bangladesh's Shidhulai Swanirvar Sangstha	9/27/2005	\$15,500
Emory University Atlanta, GA	To facilitate Emory University's collaborative effort in the project: "The DLF Distributed Library: OAI for Digital Library Aggregation"	10/1/2004	\$40,684
Foster, Nancy Rochester, NY	To facilitate a workshop on how to study faculty research behavior and implications for the library at Wesleyan University	12/20/2006	\$2,500
Foster, Nancy Rochester, NY	To facilitate a workshop on the study of faculty research behavior and its implications for the library at Kenyon University	3/26/2007	\$2,000
Kresh, Diane Washington, DC	To serve as editor/compiler of <i>The Whole Digital Library Handbook</i>	1/3/2006	\$50,000
Mitchell, Marilyn Port Townsend, WA	To write an introductory essay for and edit a series of reports on work-restructuring projects	6/1/2006	\$5,000
Mosbo, Julie Austin, TX	To develop a database of international preservation activity	5/10/2007	\$3,000
Rentfrow, Daphnee Providence, RI	To assist with the Postdoctoral Fellowship in Scholarly Information Resources program	8/1/2006	\$5,500
Rieger, Oya Ithaca, NY	To write a white paper on the impacts of mass digitization	6/4/2007	\$5,000
Shore, Elliot Bryn Mawr, PA	To organize, direct, and conduct the CLIR Postdoctoral Fellowship in Scholarly Information Resources for 2006-2007	7/1/2006	\$20,300
Stanford University Stanford, CA	To reimburse Katherine Kott for time spent in her role as director of the Digital Library Federation's Aquifer initiative	11/30/2004	\$263,400
University of Illinois Champaign, IL	To facilitate the University of Illinois' collaborative effort in the project: "The DLF Distributed Library: OAI for Digital Library Aggregation"	10/1/2004	\$66,377

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI	To facilitate the University of Michigan's collaborative effort in the project: "The DLF Distributed Library: OAI for Digital Library Aggregation"	10/1/2004	\$225,957
Zorich, Diane Princeton, NJ	To perform a survey of American-based digital humanities centers	5/24/2007	\$63,000

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2007

WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
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INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2007, and the related statement of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council on Library and Information Resources management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2007, and the results of its operations and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 26 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Herndon, Virginia
October 15, 2007

Members American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2007

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2007</u>
Assets			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 1,392,872	\$ -	\$ 1,392,872
Investments	1,651,142	1,556,719	3,207,861
Accounts receivable	332,863	-	332,863
Furniture and equipment, net	19,048	-	19,048
Other assets	<u>32,945</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>32,945</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 3,428,870</u>	<u>\$ 1,556,719</u>	<u>\$ 4,985,589</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets			
Accounts payable	\$ 128,073	\$ -	\$ 128,073
Accrued expenses	<u>42,696</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>42,696</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 170,769</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 170,769</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 3,258,101</u>	<u>\$ 1,556,719</u>	<u>\$ 4,814,820</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 3,428,870</u>	<u>\$ 1,556,719</u>	<u>\$ 4,985,589</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2007

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2007</u>
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ 2,190,000	\$ 179,285	\$ 2,369,285
Contributions	449,200	167,700	616,900
Publication sales	9,095	-	9,095
Investment income	140,028	151,049	291,077
Other income	<u>9,900</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>9,900</u>
	<u>\$ 2,798,223</u>	<u>\$ 498,034</u>	<u>\$ 3,296,257</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 1,880,892</u>	<u>\$ (1,880,892)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 4,679,115</u>	<u>\$ (1,382,858)</u>	<u>\$ 3,296,257</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation	\$ 645,337	\$ -	\$ 645,337
Leadership	457,223	-	457,223
Other	4,123	-	4,123
Cyberinfrastructure	22,022	-	22,022
The next scholar	<u>372,833</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>372,833</u>
Total Program services	\$ 1,501,538	\$ -	\$ 1,501,538
Administration	<u>651,170</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>651,170</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 2,152,708</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 2,152,708</u>
Change in Net Assets	\$ 2,526,407	\$ (1,382,858)	\$ 1,143,549
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>\$ 731,694</u>	<u>\$ 2,939,577</u>	<u>\$ 3,671,271</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 3,258,101</u>	<u>\$ 1,556,719</u>	<u>\$ 4,814,820</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2007

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ 1,143,549
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities	
Depreciation	9,856
Loss on disposal of equipment	4,454
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	(108,248)
Realized (gain)loss on investments	(57,059)
(Increase) decrease in other assets	(2,483)
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	153,421
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>(240,280)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Operating Activities	\$ <u>903,210</u>
Investing Activities	
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 3,090,094
Purchases of investments	(3,714,977)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(6,491)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Investing Activities	\$ <u>(631,374)</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ 271,836
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>1,121,036</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	\$ <u><u>1,392,872</u></u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information	
Interest paid during the year	\$ _____ -

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2007

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent sponsor fees billings, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources has not recorded any amount for the allowance for doubtful accounts because the Council on Library and Information Resources receives funds on a cost reimbursement basis and sponsorship revenues are current.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2007
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2007 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

NOTE 3 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 177,233
Leasehold improvements	<u>4,015</u>
	181,248
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(162,200)</u>
	<u>\$ 19,048</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2007
(Continued)

NOTE 4- Investments – The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, “Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations.” Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2007

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ 26,766	\$ -	\$ 1,042,429
Bonds	-	(2,903)	88,744
Corporate fixed income	(3,329)	-	1,050,000
Government securities	(48,106)	1,084	596,208
Mutual funds	<u>81,728</u>	<u>110,067</u>	<u>430,480</u>
Subtotal	\$ 57,059	\$ 108,248	\$ <u>3,207,861</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	\$ <u>804,673</u>
Total	\$ <u>57,059</u>	\$ <u>108,248</u>	

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

NOTE 6 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 7 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program (“the Plan”) administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees’ salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$85,882 in 2007.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2007
(Continued)

NOTE 8 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2007, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$4,012,534 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2007 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$520,469. Furthermore, all balances in investment accounts are uninsured.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$2,190,000 from one organization which represents 66 % of total revenue.

NOTE 9 - Accounts Receivable

	<u>June 30,</u> <u>2007</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 8,078
30 - 60 days	-
60 - 90 days	-
Over 90 days	324,785
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 332,863</u>

NOTE 10 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August 2008. The Council on Library and Information Resources subleases part of its space to the Digital Library Federation. Rental expense, net of sublease income for the year ending June 30, 2007 was \$144,479. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in June 1, 2010. Future minimum lease payments under all leases with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending <u>June 30, ____</u>	<u>Capital Lease</u>	<u>Operating Leases</u>
2008	3,588	153,760
2009	3,588	25,805
2010	<u>3,588</u>	<u>-</u>
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 10,764	<u>\$ 179,565</u>
Less: Amount representing interest. Present value of net minimum lease payments	<u>(673)</u>	
	<u>\$ 10,091</u>	

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2007
(Concluded)

NOTE 11 - Board Designated Net Assets Funds
The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 12 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments
The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. The fair values for receivables, and long term debt are based primarily on quoted market prices for those or similar instruments. A comparison of the carrying value of those financial instruments is as follows:

	<u>Carrying Value</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Assets		
Accounts receivables	\$ 332,863	\$ 332,863
Liabilities		
Capital Lease	\$ 10,091	\$ 10,091

NOTE 13 - Related Party
The Council on Library and Information Resources shares space with the Digital Library Federation. The Digital Library Federation reimburses the Council on Library and Information Resources for use of space and utilities. The Digital Library Federation paid The Council on Library and Information Resources \$12,000 for the use of space and utilities for the year ended June 30, 2007. The Council on Library and Information Resources has also entered into contracts with clients and has subcontracted with the Digital Library Federation to perform the work. The Digital Library Federation reimburses the Council on Library and Information Resources for any expenses paid by the Council on Library and Information Resources on their behalf.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

For the Year Ended June 30, 2007

	The Next Scholar	Cyberinfrastructure	Leadership	Preservation	Other	Total Program Services	Admin.	Total 2007
Employee costs	\$ 9,210	\$ 2,817	\$ 7,576	\$ 567,499	\$ -	\$ 587,102	\$ 116,762	\$ 703,864
Professional services	267,709	83,028	197,724	50,764	2,000	601,225	141,038	742,263
Communications	16,053	10	962	154	-	17,179	22,584	39,763
Travel and meetings	66,878	5,736	247,920	15,270	-	335,804	61,871	397,675
Publications	12,008	1,502	2,875	11,650	2,123	30,158	16,294	46,452
Office operations	975	(2,746)	166	-	-	(1,605)	292,621	291,016
Reimbursement	-	(68,325)	-	-	-	(68,325)	-	(68,325)
TOTAL	\$ 372,833	\$ 22,022	\$ 457,223	\$ 645,337	\$ 4,123	\$ 1,501,538	\$ 651,170	\$ 2,152,708

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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